

MULTI-AXIAL TESTING OF PLANAR COMPOSITE SPECIMENS

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SUMMARY: Multi-axial stress states are common in structural components, yet failure of composites under multi-axial loading is relatively poorly understood. This situation has arisen because it has been extremely difficult to devise reliable multi-axial test methods. As a result, conservative failure criteria have to be used, and the effect has been to increase the mass of components. Since the mid 1970s, DERA has generated a large body of multi-axial test data using tubular specimens. However, this data cannot be directly applied to flatter composite laminates. DERA has recently made considerable progress in the use of flat cruciform specimens. These cruciform specimens have been used to obtain failures originating from open-holes, filled-holes, and the sites of impact damage over the full spectrum of biaxial loading. The development of the test method and the results of tests on open holes have been presented here. This includes a discussion of detailed fractography and failure mode investigations.

KEYWORDS: test, multi-axial, bi-axial, cruciform, test-machine, fractography, failure criteria

INTRODUCTION

Efforts within the Defence Evaluation and Research Agency (DERA) to generate multi-axial data on composites started at Fort Halstead in the mid 1970s, when tubular specimens were developed to study the effects of combined loading on weapon launch-tubes. Following on from this a test rig was built that allowed internal or external pressure to be applied, as well as tensile or compressive end loading. Using this equipment the complete bi-axial failure envelope can be explored (ref. 1). Failure envelopes continue to be obtained for both virgin and damaged material. More recently, it has been possible to apply internal and external pressure simultaneously and generate tri-axial test data.

In the case of aircraft, the lack of detailed knowledge of materials behaviour has been recognised by the industry for many years, and in order to preserve safety standards, it has been necessary to use design criteria that are highly conservative. As many applications, including aircraft

structure, make extensive use of flat and gently curved panels, which are constructed rather differently from tubes, data from the latter cannot be read across directly. However, the understanding of failure criteria that has resulted from the work on tubes is of general value (refs.2, 3). In 1993, DERA's acquisition of a 500kN bi-axial test machine, and the development of planar cruciform specimens started to transform the situation. Since then, the cruciform testing programme has expanded so that it now involves 5 industrial partners. The success of the programme has been such that a second test-machine has recently been purchased with a 1500kN capacity.

By the rotation of axes, any in-plane stress-state can be resolved into orthogonal principal stresses. Consequently, any desired multi-axial stress state can be generated at the centre of the cruciform by cutting the specimen in the appropriate direction and applying the appropriate combination of loads on the two axes. To date, the cruciform work has mainly concentrated on the many practical bi-axial stress-states which can be generated in realistic laminates whose material axes are coincident with the specimen axes.

Figure 1: Assembled biaxial specimen

Early work concentrated on the development of the test technique, and on obtaining a failure envelope for open-holes in carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy over the entire spectrum of biaxial loading. Following the success of that work, the test programme has expanded considerably, but the only findings which can be released at present are those presented here for open-holes. The programme has proceeded to address: fastener-filled holes, impact-damaged laminates, impact-damaged sandwich-panels, fatigue around open-holes, fatigue around impact damage sites, fastener-filled holes in double or single-shear, environmentally conditioned laminates, joints in substructure, ply-drop-offs, other lay-ups, other thicknesses, and mixed-woven laminates.

SPECIMEN DESIGN

The key to successful biaxial testing is the design of the specimen (refs.4 & 5). Considerable effort has been devoted to developing a specimen that can achieve failures at stress-raising features in realistic high-strength carbon-fibre laminates over the full spectrum of biaxial loading. In fact, it was found that the design of the specimen drives the design of the test-machine. The challenges in specimen design included: prevention of premature failure at the corners of the cruciform (arm junctions), obtaining a uniform strain-field within the test-region, minimising the applied-load needed, prevention of buckling under compressive loading, and prevention of failure at the interface with the test-machine grips.

Reducing the stress-concentrations at the corners of the cruciform is essential if the specimen is to be used over the full spectrum of biaxial loading. These stress concentrations are highest for equal tension-tension and equal compression-compression loading, and are lowest for tension-compression loading. Initially, the specimen design was optimised for the critical tension-tension load case. The stress concentrations at the corners of the cruciform were reduced sufficiently to allow failure at open holes to be achieved for the tension-tension case. It then followed that valid failures would be obtainable for all other loading cases. The measures taken to reduce the stress concentrations were considered to be an improvement upon other designs in the literature. Modifications to the specimen design can be made to optimise the performance or to reduce the cost for different lay-ups, features, and applied-load ratios.

The design of a typical specimen is presented in Figure 1. The 2mm thick carbon-fibre composite test-material is sandwiched between glass-fibre composite cladding with a central circular cut-out exposing the carbon-fibre test-region. Aluminium end-tabs are bonded to the specimen, and holes are drilled through the specimen to accommodate bolts from the test-machine grips. The bolts are used to clamp the grips: they do not bear upon the specimen.

Figure 2: Typical photoelasticity analysis of an open-hole

SPECIMEN VALIDATION

Extensive validation and calibration of the strain in the test-region has been undertaken using both strain gauge and photo-elasticity techniques (Figure 2). These trials have demonstrated that the variations of strain within the test-region are low, and that the tests are repeatable. Detailed fractography has been used throughout the work, both to validate that failure initiated at the feature of interest, and to identify the failure mechanisms. To date, the degree of scatter in the results has been found to be surprisingly low.

TEST PROCEDURE

Generally, the test region of a specimen is strain gauged before it is installed in the machine (Figure 3). However, when testing a specimen with a central feature, such as an open hole, the global strain-level within the test region cannot be accurately determined using strain gauges. This is because the strain field is disturbed by the presence of the hole (Figure 2). To overcome this, specimens are calibrated before the feature is added to the test-region. This enables the test-operator to determine the displacement ramps that will generate the required strain-state in the test-region. Since variations in the response of the specimens have been found to be small, it is often acceptable to calibrate only a very small number of specimens.

Figure 3: 500kN Bi-axial test-machine, with specimen and anti-buckling guide installed

Calibration involves applying a range of displacement ramps to the specimen, and noting the strain-state at the centre of the test region. If the strain-states at which failures are required are known, then the ratios of applied displacement can be tuned accurately. Good first estimates of the displacement ratios can be obtained from the finite-element analysis of the specimen.

The test-machines use four servo-hydraulic actuators and a special control system to ensure that the centre of the specimen is not displaced during loading. This ensures that each pair of arms is equally loaded, and that no side-loads are placed on either the specimen or the actuators. A data-logging computer is used to record the strain measurements from a strain-gauge amplifier, and the force and displacement outputs from the test machine. The strain-state at failure is calculated by multiplying the specimen stiffnesses obtained during calibration by the applied loads at failure.

The presence of the cladding is beneficial in that it arrests fractures once they have grown to the edge of the test-region. This prevents catastrophic failure of the whole specimen and thereby prevents uneven loading of the test-machine actuators.

PREVENTION OF BUCKLING UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADS

It was expected that support would be required to prevent buckling of the specimen when significant compressive loading was applied on either one axis or both axes. The buckling performance of the specimen under tensile-compressive and compressive-compressive loading was investigated theoretically using finite-element analysis. This confirmed the need for an anti-buckling support. Under equal compressive-compressive loading, which was the most critical case, the 2mm thick test-region buckled at a theoretical load of 72kN. This was considerably less than the 500kN load that the machine was capable of applying. The analysis also indicated that buckling was confined to the test region and taper for compressive loads (P_x) up to at least 314kN. When additional constraints were applied to the cladding, excluding the tapered region, buckling was predicted to occur at 854kN under equal compressive-compressive loading. This exceeds the 500kN limit and leaves a margin to allow for any inconsistencies in the alignment or machining of the tapers.

An anti-buckling support was designed to provide rigid support of the test region, cladding and taper, to provide freedom around the central feature (e.g. hole) in the test region, to accommodate strain gauges on the test region, and to provide compatibility with specimens of various thicknesses. The support was also required to be light and durable. The support design was refined until it reached the form illustrated in Figure 4. The specimen is constrained between two sandwich-panels that, once bolted together, support the cladded area of the specimen.

The test-region is supported by adjustable plugs that pass through circular cutouts in the sandwich panels. This arrangement accommodates specimens with various test-material and cladding thicknesses. Cutouts in the faces of the interchangeable test-region plugs accommodate strain gauges, and provide freedom around the open hole so that fracture mechanisms are unrestrained. The strain gauge wires pass through recesses in the plug faces and out between the sandwich panel and the plug.

Anti-buckling support of the tapered region of each specimen is provided by Hysol EA934 shimming-adhesive, which fills the gap between the cladding taper and the sandwich panel. Since

the modulus of the shimming adhesive is lower than that of the cladding, it is anticipated that increases in peel and interlaminar shear stress at the tip of the taper should be negligible.

Figure 4: Assembly of the anti-buckling guide

SPECIMENS CONTAINING OPEN HOLES

Specific procedures adopted for open-hole specimens are as follows. After calibration, each specimen is removed from the machine. A hole of 6mm diameter is then drilled through the centre of the test region. Care is taken during the drilling operation to ensure that the hole is cleanly drilled and that splitting does not occur on the back face. The specimen is then reinstalled in the test machine as before. The specimen is then tested to failure at the required biaxial strain ratio using the test ramp determined during calibration. Specimens are then photographed, inspected using ultrasonic C-scanning and subjected to X-ray radiography using penetrant, opaque to X-rays, to show details of cracking.

TEST RESULTS FOR OPEN HOLE SPECIMENS

The global biaxial strains at failure are illustrated as a failure envelope in Figure 5. There was significantly less scatter in the part of the envelope dominated by compressive failures. The

specimens tested at biaxial strain ratios of (1 : 0.9) and (1 : 1) did not fail at the central hole but at the cruciform corners. The arrows on the data points shown in the failure envelope indicate that these failures were invalid. The data points therefore represent minimum values of failure strain; i.e. a valid failure would have occurred at higher strain. These corner failures could have been prevented, but only by employing measures which would have increased the applied-load requirement. In this particular case, the load applied for the (1:1) strain ratio was already at the limit of the 500kN test-machine. Valid failures have been achieved at open holes under (1:1) loading in tests on other CFRP materials.

The global failure-strain envelope was approximately rectangular in shape. It is possible that the envelope extends to higher strains in the (1 : 1) corner for the reasons given above. The failure envelope in Figure 6 shows the global stresses at failure.

Figure 5: Biaxial strain at failure

Figure 6: Biaxial stress at failure

A TYPICAL FAILURE ANALYSIS

In most cases, comprehensive failure analysis and fractography is conducted on the specimens. In this paper the analysis of a failure at an open-hole at a strain-ratio of (-0.66:1.0) is presented as an example.

The surface of the specimen did not reveal the extent of the sub-surface damage (Figures 7 & 8). The surface plies contained splitting and lines of fibre-breakage that ran along the line of fracture, with little out-of-plane distortion. The surface plies had suffered only a small amount of fibre fracture; they contained a large number of angle-ply splits and were largely delaminated. This indicated that the surface plies must have delaminated early in the failure process. If this had not been the case there would have been more evidence of surface fibre fracture.

The X-ray of this specimen (Figure 9) showed the two major failures at right angles to one another forming an X through the specimen test area. One fracture was tensile (A-A) the other compressive (B-B). The compressive failure was approximately straight and parallel to the 90° fibres, the tensile failure snaked a little and was approximately parallel to the 0° fibres. Delaminations associated with the compressive and tensile fractures interacted around the hole to form a parallelogram pattern; about 50mm across corners. Transverse cracking was evident in the region of tensile failure and angle-ply splitting had occurred in the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. On the X-ray, there was little evidence of longitudinal splitting.

Figure 7
Photograph of test-region after failure

Figure 8
C-Scan of test-region after failure

The 90° fibres had failed in tension. The details of the fibre ends and the tensile fracture pattern generally indicated that the tensile fracture had propagated outwards from the edge of the hole. Longitudinal splitting was seen under the SEM, this split length was approx. 1-2mm. There appeared to be more transverse cracking in the tension failure than normally occurs in a uni-axially-loaded specimen. The 0° plies were observed to have failed in a compressive mode. On the fracture BB, there was evidence of flexure or buckling: tensile fractures were observed toward one face, and compressive toward the other. There was also some out-of-plane fibre micro-buckling damage in the 0° plies close to the edge of the hole.

Figure 9: X-ray of failed specimen

It has not yet been determined whether the remaining laminate buckled and failed in compression along (B-B) first and then failed in tension along (A-A) in the orthogonal direction, or vice versa. The first possible scenario is that the loss of the outer surface plies could have led to a buckling flexure of the remaining laminate. This then caused the compression fracture (B-B) which subsequently gave rise to a tensile failure along (A-A). The second scenario is that after the separation of the surface plies the remaining laminate failed in tension along (A-A) and the fractured parts then buckled and failed in flexure along (B-B).

The presence of some out-of-plane fibre micro-buckling damage in the 0° plies would indicate that compressive failure by fibre micro-buckling had occurred before or during ultimate failure. The delaminated surface plies meant that the 0° plies were only partially restrained and therefore out-of-plane fibre micro-buckling would have been more likely to occur.

CONCLUSIONS

The capability developed in this work, which allows failure to be investigated under tension-tension, tension-compression and compression-compression biaxial loading, is unique in Europe, possibly in the world. Failure at an open hole, typical of the multitudes of fastener holes found in many structures, has been successfully investigated over the full spectrum of biaxial loading. The method is currently being applied to the investigation of failure at a range of stress-raising features under both static and fatigue loading.

The global-strain failure envelope is broadly rectangular in shape. In the tension-compression quadrant, the corner of the envelope appears to be in the region of (1 : -0.66) rather than (1 : -1). This could be due to the transition from a tension-dominated failure to a compression-dominated failure, and the fact that the criteria for tension and compression failure differ. Fractographic examinations have increased our understanding of failure at the hole. They are supporting the development of physically-based failure-criteria which are key to the efficient design of composite structures.

A key observation is that although much higher elastic stress-concentrations occur under tension-compression loading than for tension-tension loading, failures under both loadings occurred at similar strain levels. This suggests that although damage initiates earlier under tension-compression loading, final failure is delayed significantly by the presence of that damage.

It is interesting to note that there was more scatter in the tension-dominated failures than there was in the compression-dominated failures. This may be due to differences in the failure mechanisms. Prior to tensile failure, a damage zone is formed which consists of 0° shear cracks, $\pm 45^\circ$ cracks, transverse matrix cracks and delaminations; this reduces the stress concentration at the hole. Scatter could be associated with variability in the extent of cracking within the damage zone. There are probably fewer mechanisms associated with a compression failure, since the specimen fails primarily by fibre micro-buckling which is more dependant on matrix and fibre stiffness; some 0° splitting may occur which would blunt the notch.

For tension-tension and compression-compression loading, tensile and compressive failures were seen that were broadly similar to those seen in the respective uniaxial tests. However, at other load ratios, the situation can be more complex. Under approximately equal tension-tension loading, the global strain at failure was found to increase.

A calibration procedure has been developed and implemented over the full spectrum of biaxial loading. This means that the biaxial loads and displacements applied at the grips can be related to the global biaxial-strains in the test region. Reproducibility of strains in the test region, between specimens under the same applied displacements, was found to be better than 6%.

In the study presented here, valid failures have been achieved at an open hole over most of the spectrum of biaxial loading, i.e. tension-tension, tension-compression and compression-compression loading. Difficulties have been experienced with some composites for biaxial loading close to equal tension-tension and equal compression-compression loading. For these cases, the stress concentrations in the cruciform corners and the applied-load requirement are both at their maximum values. However, valid failures have been achieved over the full spectrum of biaxial loading for other composites.

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REFERENCES

- 1 A S Kaddour, P D Soden, "*Failure of ± 55 Degree Filament Wound Composite Tubes under Biaxial Compression*", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.32, No. 18/1998
- 2 P D Soden, M J Hinton, A S Kaddour, "*A comparison of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminate*", Composites Science and Technology 58 (1998) 1225-1254
- 3 M J Hinton, P D Soden, "*Predicting failure in composite laminates: The background to the exercise*", Composite Science and Technology 58 (1998) 1001-1010
- 4 R C Dadey, "*Failure of Notched Carbon Fibre Composites Under Biaxial Tension-Compression Loading*". DRA Customer Report DRA/AS/MS/CR93034/1.0, December 1993.
- 5 P J Hopgood and P J Mobbs, "*Design and validation of a specimen for a biaxial test machine*". DRA Customer Report DRA/SMC/CR941019/1.0, June 1994

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